

List of the 22 anions of interest that were finally included in the validation proposal:

Analytes	Obtained from
Azide	Sodium azide
Benzoate	Potassium benzoate
Bromate	Sodium bromate
Bromide	Sodium bromide
Chlorate	Potassium chlorate
Chloride	Sodium chloride
Chromate	Sodium chromate
Cyanate	Sodium cyanate
Formate	Calcium formate
Iodate	Potassium iodate
Iso-phthalate	Iso-phthalic acid / Benzene-1,3-dicarboxylic acid
Nitrate	Potassium nitrate
Nitrite	Sodium nitrite
Oxalate	Oxalic acid
Perchlorate	Potassium perchlorate
Phosphate	Disodium phosphate
Phthalate	o-Phthalic acid / Benzene-1,2-dicarboxylic acid
Sulfate	Sodium sulphate
Tartrate	Tartaric acid
Therephthate	Therephthalic acid / Benzene-1,4-dicarboxylic acid
Thiocyanate	Potassium thiocyanate
Thiosulfate	Potassium thiosulfate

List of Cations of interest:

Analytes	Formula	Obtained from
Lithium	Li ⁺	Lithium nitrate
Sodium	Na ⁺	Sodium chloride
Potassium	K ⁺	Potassium nitrate
Cesium	Cs ⁺	Cesium nitrate
Ammonium	NH ₄ ⁺	Ammonium nitrate
Ethylammonium	C ₂ H ₅ N ⁺	Ethylammonium chloride
Urea	NH ₂ CONH ₂ N ⁺	Urea
Dicyandiamide	C ₂ H ₄ N ₄ ⁺	Dicyandiamide
Magnesium	Mg ²⁺	Magnesium nitrate hexahydrate
Calcium	Ca ²⁺	Calcium sulfate dihydrate
Strontium	Sr ²⁺	Strontium nitrate
Barium	Ba ²⁺	Barium nitrate
Manganese	Mn ²⁺	Manganese(II) sulfate monohydrate
Iron	Fe ²⁺	Iron(II) chloride
Cobalt	Co ²⁺	Cobalt(II) chloride
Nickel	Ni ²⁺	Nickel(II) chloride
Copper	Cu ²⁺	Copper(II) chloride
Zinc	Zn ²⁺	Zinc chloride
Cadmium	Cd ²⁺	Cadmium chloride hydrate
Aluminium	Al ²⁺	Aluminium sulfate hydrate
Lead	Pb ²⁺	Lead(II) chloride
Gadolinium	Gd ³⁺	Gadolinium (III) chloride hexahydrate

